

Supplementary information for
**Sharp 660-km discontinuity controlled by extremely narrow binary post-spinel
transition**

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24.75(4) GPa, 1,700 K, $\kappa = 0-7.2^\circ$, 150 s, $2\theta = 7.2^\circ$

Extended Data Figure 1. The X-ray diffraction pattern of an MgO pressure marker just after reaching a temperature of 1700 K from run M2263. (b) is an enlargement of the high-energy side of the profile shown in (a). The eight diffraction peaks of MgO up to the index of 422 were typically used for pressure determination. Only tiny diamond peaks (marked by “Dia”) were observed as a secondary phase in the profile.

(a) Before compression (M2258)

(b) 7 MN

(c) Typical slit sizes

Extended Data Figure 2. Radiographic images of the sample from the run M2258. (a) Before compression. Fo_{100} and Fo_{70} are the samples with bulk compositions of Mg_2SiO_4 and $(\text{Mg}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_{0.3})_2\text{SiO}_4$, respectively. TC: thermocouple. (b) At a press load of 7 MN and before heating. Dashed lines are boundaries between the samples and MgO pressure marker. (c) The typical slit sizes of the incident beam, which are two dimensional areas obtained diffracted X-rays, for the samples and MgO pressure marker (P.M.) (the maximum value was $700\ \mu\text{m}$ vertically).

Extended Data Figure 3. Schematic cross-sections of the cell assembly. Two sintered samples and a sintered MgO pressure marker (P.M.) were set at the center of the cell assembly. Fo₁₀₀ and Fo₇₀ denote the samples with bulk compositions of Mg₂SiO₄ and (Mg_{0.7}Fe_{0.3})₂SiO₄, respectively.

Extended Data Figure 4. A back-scattered electron image of the sample recovered from 23.72 GPa and 1700 K (M2272). The white, light-grey and dark-grey grains are bridgmanite, ringwoodite and periclase, respectively. Typical grain sizes of bridgmanite and periclase are 1–3 μm , which is comparable to those of enstatite and periclase in the starting material, respectively. Bulk ringwoodite grains (2–6 μm) surround bridgmanite and periclase grains, separating each other and impeding the complete reversal reaction between bridgmanite and periclase. Brg, Pc, and Rw indicate bridgmanite, periclase and ringwoodite, respectively.

Extended Data Figure 5. *In situ* X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples. (a) Changes of X-ray diffraction patterns of the $(\text{Mg}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_{0.3})_2\text{SiO}_4$ sample from the run M2268. The starting samples (I) were first compressed to 28.49(8) GPa at room temperature, and then heated to 1100 K to convert into an assemblage of ringwoodite + akimotoite + ferropericlase (II), where the pressure decreased to 22.92(5) GPa. While the samples were kept at a constant temperature of 1100 K, press load was increased to a desired pressure of ~23 GPa, obtaining a pressure of 23.57(8) GPa as a result (III). After a check that pressure did not change within the errors, the temperature was increased to 1700 K within 5 min. After reaching the temperature, an X-ray diffraction collection of the pressure marker was immediately started, and then those of the samples were conducted (IV). (b) Comparison of X-ray diffraction patterns in Mg_2SiO_4 (lower) and $(\text{Mg}_{0.7}\text{Fe}_{0.3})_2\text{SiO}_4$ (upper) obtained at a pressure of 23.86(6) GPa and a temperature of 1700 K from the run M2268. The iron-free sample shows the high-pressure assemblage (bridgmanite + periclase), whereas the iron-bearing one shows the low-pressure assemblage (ringwoodite + ferropericlase + stishovite). The minerals in the parentheses are phases present. The diffraction angle 2θ was fixed to 7.2° . Ol: olivine; En: enstatite; Rw: ringwoodite; Ak: akimotoite; Brg: bridgmanite; Pc: periclase; $f\text{Pc}$: ferropericlase; St: stishovite; Dia: diamond/epoxy (see Extended Data Fig. 3).

Extended Data Table 1. Experimental conditions and phases present at 1700 K.

Run no.	^a P_{3BM} (GPa)	^b P_{vinet} (GPa)	^c Av. P (GPa)	^d Time (min)	Run products ^e Mg ₂ SiO ₄	(Mg _{0.7} Fe _{0.3}) ₂ SiO ₄
M2272	23.56 (5)	23.88 (5)	23.72 (5)	60	^f Rw+Brg+Pc	Rw+fPc+St
M2268	23.70 (6)	24.02 (6)	23.86 (6)	100	Brg+Pc	Rw+fPc+St
M1991	23.83 (5)	24.16 (5)	24.00 (5)	120	Brg+Pc	Brg+fPc+St

Abbreviations: Rw, ringwoodite; Brg, bridgmanite; Pc, periclase; *f*Pc, ferropiclase; St, stishovite.

^a Pressures calculated from the third-order Birch-Murnaghan (3BM) equation of states (EOS) of MgO by Ref. 18.

^b Pressures calculated from the Vinet EOS of MgO by Ref. 18.

^c Average run pressures just after reaching 1700 K between pressures obtained with 3BM and Vinet EOSs were adopted.

^d Duration in keeping temperature at 1700 K.

^e Data of phase identification for Mg₂SiO₄ were referred to Ref. 12.

^f Stable phase in these runs were identified as Rw (Ref. 12 and see the Methods section).

Numbers in parentheses represent standard deviation.

Extended Data Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters in the calculation shown in Fig.

1.

	Data	Reference
^{a,b} $X_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{Brg}}$	$-0.043+9.5\times 10^{-5}\times(T-273)$	14
^c $\Delta_{\text{Brg-fPc}}G^0_{P,T}$ (J/mol)	$24.1\times 10^3+3.5\times T$	15
^d $\Delta_{\text{Rw-fPc}}G^0_{P,T}$ (J/mol)	$912+4.15\times(T-298)+18.9\times 10\times P$	16
^e $W^{\text{Brg}}_{\text{Mg-Fe}}$ (kJ/mol)	-4.9 (7.6)	15
^e $W^{\text{fPc}}_{\text{Mg-Fe}}$ (kJ/mol)	12.1 (1.8)	17
^e $W^{\text{Rw}}_{\text{Mg-Fe}}$ (kJ/mol)	3.5 (1.0)	16

^aFe/(Fe+Mg) assuming all Fe is ferrous.

^bObtained from a linear fitting of the temperature-composition (maximum solubility of FeO) relationship in bridgmanite

^c T is in Kelvin.

^d T is in Kelvin and P is in GPa.

^eValues were changed in the ranges of errors to be consistent with the present result (see the Methods section).

Numbers in parentheses represent standard deviation.

$\Delta_{\text{Psp tr.}}V^{\text{Mg}}_{P,T}$ was calculated using thermochemical and thermoelastic parameters shown in Extended Data Table 3 based on the third-order Birch-Murnaghan equation of state.

Extended Data Table 3. Thermochemical and thermoelastic parameters used in the calculation of the binary loop and latent heat of the post-spinel transition.

Phase	* V_{Mg}	* V_{Fe}	K_0	$K'_{T,0}$	$(\partial K_{T,0}/\partial T)_P$	$\alpha_0 \times 10^5$	$\alpha_1 \times 10^8$
	cm ³ /mol	cm ³ /mol	/GPa		/GPa·K ⁻¹	/K ⁻¹	/K ⁻²
Brg	24.45 ^a	29.43 ^a	272 ^b	4 ^b	-0.017 ^c	1.17 ^c	1.51 ^c
Rw	39.65 ^a	42.02 ^a	187 ^d	4.41 ^d	-0.028 ^d	1.90 ^d	1.20 ^d
<i>f</i> Pc	11.25 ^a	12.25 ^a	159 ^e	4 ^e	-0.029 ^f	3.45 ^f	1.14 ^f
$\dagger C_P = A + BT^{-0.5} + CT^{-2} + DT^{-3}$ (J/mol/K)							
	A×10 ⁻²	B×10 ⁻³	C×10 ⁻⁶	D×10 ⁻⁸			
Brg ^g	1.769	-1.565	0	2.157			
Pc ^h	0.586	-0.189	-1.664	0.234			
Rw ⁱ	2.178	-1.543	-0.569	-4.1921			

Abbreviations: Rw, ringwoodite; Brg, bridgmanite; *f*Pc, ferropericlase.

a, Ref. 43; b, Ref. 44; c, Ref. 45; d, Ref. 46; e, Ref. 47; f, Ref. 48; g, Ref. 49; h, Ref. 50; i, Ref. 51.

Thermal expansivity is expressed as $\alpha_{T,0} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 T$.

Volumes at 23.4 GPa and 2000 K were calculated with the third-order Birch-Murnaghan equation of state.

*Volumes (V_{Mg} and V_{Fe}) of Mg- and Fe-endmembers of each phase, respectively. Volumes of Brg + *f*Pc and Rw were calculated at $X_{\text{Mg}} = 0.9$ using a linear relationship of volume change between V_{Mg} and V_{Fe} of each phase, in which Mg-Fe partition coefficient between Brg and *f*Pc ($[X_{\text{Fe}}/X_{\text{Mg}}]_{\text{Brg}}/[X_{\text{Fe}}/X_{\text{Mg}}]_{\text{Pc}}$) of 0.25¹⁵ was used to estimate X_{Mg} of Brg and *f*Pc.

$\dagger C_P$ of Mg-endmembers was used in the calculation.

Supplementary discussion

Thermodynamic modelling of the 660-km discontinuity

Even in the FeO-MgO-Al₂O₃-SiO₂-O₂ system (allowing redox reactions) up to quite high oxygen fugacities, ringwoodite (Rw) and ferropericlase (fPc) can be adequately described as binary Fe²⁺-Mg solid solutions^{52,53}. In contrast, magnesium-silicate perovskite (bridgmanite (Brg)) can accept both aluminium and ferric iron⁵³. So too can garnet (Gt)⁵⁵. For this reason, alumina content and redox state can potentially affect the transition pressure and width of the Rw-breakdown reaction (post-spinel (Psp) transition), which involves reactions between all of these phases.

In a number of different studies, it has been shown that in a ~200 K temperature range around average mantle geotherms, a number of different reactions can take place around the Psp transition in pyrolitic compositions^{38,56}. At low temperatures, Brg exists at pressures below the Psp transition, while at high temperatures, fPc is stable. In both cases, Gt exists both sides of the reaction.

Although the pressure interval of the Psp transition have not previously been measured in experiments, the very minor change in Brg and fPc compositions across the Psp transition in pyrolitic compositions^{38,57} suggests that the pressure interval is narrow in these compositions. In the following modeling, we outline how the addition of Al³⁺, Fe³⁺ and metallic iron affect the pressure interval of the Psp transition. The figures in this document are intended to show the effects of adding alumina and autoredox (the transformation of ferrous iron into ferric and metallic iron) - these effects are quite general, and are not unique to any particular model choices. Calculations are undertaken using PerpleX⁵⁸ and BurnMan⁵⁹.

1. FeO-MgO-SiO₂ (FMS) system

The experiments in this study are conducted in the FMS system. They can be readily compared with datasets such as Ref. 60 (Figure S1) and Ref. 56 (Figure S2).

The $Rw \rightarrow Brg + fPc$ transition (hereafter referred to as the Psp transition) in the FMS system can be described via the following two equations:

The narrow pressure interval over which the Psp transition takes place is a consequence of the partitioning of Fe and Mg between the coexisting phases. Over the range of FeO contents expected in the mantle, the compositions of Brg and fPc in equilibrium with a mantle-like Rw are very similar to the compositions of Brg and fPc coexisting with each other after the Psp transition.

As bulk compositions increase in SiO₂ content, the pressure interval narrows as the ability of Brg to buffer the Fe:Mg ratio of the coexisting phases increases (Figures S3a and S4a). The pressure of the transition will also increase, as a result of a lower Fe:Mg ratio in Brg than Rw and the positive dependence of Fe₂SiO₄ content on the Psp transition pressure.

Figure S1: Binary phase diagrams constructed using Ref. 60. Rw: ringwoodite; Brg: bridgmanite; fPc: ferropericlasite; St: stishovite.

Figure S2: Binary phase diagrams constructed using Ref. 56. Rw: ringwoodite; Brg: bridgmanite; fPc: ferropericlase; St: stishovite.

2. FeO-MgO-Al₂O₃-SiO₂ (FMAS) system

Assuming pyrolitic FeO:MgO:SiO₂ ratios, we can investigate the effect of adding alumina (Figures S3b and S4b).

In order to understand the common characteristics of these figures, it is useful to consider the following equilibrium relations:

$$\mu_{\text{MgSiO}_3} - \mu_{\text{MgO}} = \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}$$

$$\mu_{\text{FeSiO}_3} - \mu_{\text{FeO}} = \mu_{\text{SiO}_2}$$

The addition of an Al₂O₃ component to Brg will decrease the activity and chemical potential of both MgSiO₃ and FeSiO₃. The change in Mg-Fe partitioning between phases is minor (e.g. Ref. 61), thus the chemical potential of SiO₂ will also decrease. This decrease in SiO₂ chemical potential will destabilise Rw, reducing the pressure of the Psp transition (both sides). At low Al₂O₃ contents, the pressure interval of the Psp transition widens, as a result of dilution of the Al₂O₃ component in Brg during the Psp transition. Adding further Al₂O₃ to the bulk composition saturates the system in Gt, which then effectively buffers the Al content of Brg. As a result, the Psp transition in the presence of Gt is very similar to that in the simpler FMS system. The increase in modal proportion of Brg during the Psp transition contributes to the breakdown of Gt by the reaction $\text{Mg}_3\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{12} \rightarrow 3\text{MgSiO}_3 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$.

Conclusion for the FMAS system: As long as the alumina content is large enough to stabilise Gt, the pressure interval of the Psp transition will be similar to that in the FMS system.

Figure S3: Binary phase diagrams constructed using Ref. 60. (a) Fo_{90} - En_{90} section. (b) Simplified FMS pyrolite and variable alumina. Fo_{90} : $(\text{Mg}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1})_2\text{SiO}_4$; En : $(\text{Mg}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1})\text{SiO}_3$; Rw : ringwoodite; Ak : akimotoite; Brg : bridgmanite; Gt : garnet; fPc : ferropericlase; St : stishovite.

Figure S4: Binary phase diagrams constructed using Ref. 56. (a) Fo_{90} - En_{90} section. (b) Simplified FMS pyrolite and variable alumina. Fo_{90} : $(\text{Mg}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1})_2\text{SiO}_4$; En : $(\text{Mg}_{0.9}\text{Fe}_{0.1})\text{SiO}_3$; Rw : ringwoodite; Ak : akimotoite; Brg : bridgmanite; Gt : garnet; fPc : ferropericlasite; St : stishovite.

3. FeO-MgO-Al₂O₃-SiO₂-O₂ (FMASO) system

Ferric endmembers in Brg and Gt open the possibility that autoredox reactions may take place, whereby ferrous iron in the silicate phases reacts to form ferric iron and metallic iron ($3\text{Fe}^{2+} \leftrightarrow 2\text{Fe}^{3+} + \text{Fe}^0$). Using the endmembers FeAlO_3 in Brg and $\text{Fe}_3\text{Fe}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{12}$ (skiagite) in Gt, two independent redox reactions are:

Considering these two reactions, we can predict the effect on the pressure interval of the Psp transition: If Rw could decompose in the absence of any other reactions, it would dilute the FeAlO_3 component in Brg. The first equilibrium above will act to counteract this dilution, causing the breakdown of further Rw, and thus narrowing the pressure interval of the Psp transition. By removing some Fe^{2+} from the system, the pressure of the transition also decreases. The first equilibrium also acts to break down Gt. If Gt contains ferric iron, then the second equilibrium will counteract this breakdown, moderating the decrease in the pressure interval. The importance of the second equilibrium will depend on the relative amounts of aluminium and ferric iron on the octahedral site(s) of Gt. Making the assumption that aluminium dominates, it is the first equilibrium that will dominate, and the pressure interval of the Psp transition will be intermediate between the FMAS system (e.g. Figure S4) and the FMASO system considering ferric iron only in Brg (e.g. Figure S5).

Figure S5: Binary phase diagram constructed using Ref. 56. Simplified FMSO pyrolite (allowing redox in Brg and variable alumina). Iron is taken from Ref. 62, and FeAlO₃ is constructed as a mechanical mixture of Al₂O₃-Brg and hematite (0.5 moles each), with a linear Gibbs free energy correction (in J/mol) equal to $-53e3-0.23e-6*P[\text{Pa}]$. The pressure correction produces an equation of state similar to that proposed previously^{63,64}, while the energetic correction produces an FeAlO₃:AlAlO₃ Brg ratio which is similar to that reported in Refs. 54 and 61. In the absence of other data, we have chosen to use X-FeAlO₃ endmember interaction energies that are equal to X-AlAlO₃ interaction energies. AlAlO₃-FeAlO₃ exchange is assumed to be ideal. In pyrolitic compositions, there are large trade-offs between X-FeAlO₃ interaction terms and the standard state FeAlO₃ free energy, so the exact details of the model are unimportant to the conclusions in this study.

We note that there are few published studies on the ferric iron content of high-pressure Gt. Existing studies suggest that ferric iron contents in Gt increase with increasing pressure⁵⁵. Within majoritic garnet (Mj-Gt), the proportion of iron in ferric form increases with iron content⁵⁶. In pyrolitic compositions, iron concentrations in Gt around 23 GPa are 0.2–0.3 on a 12-oxygen basis, which implies a low ferric iron content [$\text{Fe}^{3+}/\Sigma\text{Fe} \sim 0.05^{65}$]. However, we stress that more experiments are needed to better understand the effects of oxygen fugacity and composition on the ferric iron content of Gt, especially in the light of the high ferric iron contents at metal saturation reported in Ref. 55.

Conclusion for the FMASO system: In the likely situation that ferric iron in Gt is less abundant than alumina content, the pressure interval of the Psp transition will be less than or similar to that in the simple FMS system.

4. FeO-MgO-Al₂O₃-SiO₂-H₂O-O₂ (FMASHO) system

Rw can accept several thousand ppm water (as hydroxyl) under lower mantle conditions. In contrast, Brg and fPc can probably only host tens of ppm. Thus, we expect hydrated mantle to melt when passing through the 660-km discontinuity*.

If hydrogen contents are sufficiently high to cause melting, hydration of the mantle has the capacity to dramatically reduce the seismic velocity jump across the 660-km discontinuity, or even change its sign. If the melt is interconnected (i.e. for dihedral angles <60 degrees), then less than a percent of melt is required to reduce seismic velocities by several percent (Ref. 66, and references therein). With this much melt released, the Psp transition would mark the upper edge of a low-velocity zone on the mantle. Such a zone has not yet been imaged. The closest observations are those of Ref. 67, who imaged a patchy uppermost lower mantle.

There is currently no accurate quantitative work on the composition of hydrous melts in equilibrium with pyrolite at the top of the lower mantle, but hydrous melts around the 410-km discontinuity are thought to be FeO- and H₂O-rich and MgO- and Al₂O₃ poor⁶⁶. If the same is true of hydrous melts produced by the breakdown of hydrous Rw, then melting will deplete the solid phases in FeO. This is likely to reduce the pressure interval of the Psp transition.

* The water capacities of Gt and calcium perovskite (Cpv) are currently poorly constrained, but probably >1000 ppm. With the low proportions of these minerals (<20 mol% Cpv (3 oxygen basis), <10 mol% Gt (12 oxygen basis)), they will be unable to hold the amount of hydrogen released from a saturated Rw.

Conclusion for the FMASHO system: Hydrogen has the potential to change the sign of the velocity jump across Psp transition by inducing melting. However, it is unlikely to significantly broaden the transition, unless Cpv or Gt are able to host significant water.

5. Natural pyrolitic compositions

Minor components not considered in the above discussion include CaO (3.29 mol% in Sun and McDonough pyrolite), and Na₂O (0.3 mol%).

CaO predominantly partitions into Gt below 20 GPa, with increasing proportions hosted by Cpv, and NAL (the “New” aluminous phase) at higher pressure⁵⁶. The growth of Cpv can largely be modeled via the reaction:

This reaction takes place over a pressure interval of >2 GPa, and has little influence on the width of the Psp interval, other than marginally affecting the stability field of Gt, which acts as a chemical buffer (see FMAS section).

Na₂O preferentially partitions into Mg-Gt throughout most of the mantle transition zone, before becoming incorporated into NAL at the base of the Rw field and uppermost lower mantle⁵⁶. Again, the growth of NAL takes place over several GPa, and has little influence on the width of the Psp transition interval.

Other constituents not included in the analysis above are very minor (K₂O, MnO, NiO, Cr₂O₃, and TiO₂ all have concentrations <0.2 mol%). They will substitute readily in the considered solid solutions, and will therefore have a limited influence on the Psp transition.

Conclusion for natural pyrolitic compositions: The dominant reactions governing the pressure interval of the Psp transition are probably confined to the FMASO system. Other components are either hosted in phases which do not play an important role in this reaction, or are too minor to significantly influence the reaction.

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